

A Comparison of Some Test Statistics for Testing the Regression Coefficients in the Ridge Probit Regression Model: Simulation and Application

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Abstract: Ridge regression is a method that has been proposed to solve the multicollinearity problem in both linear and non-linear regression models. This paper studies different Ridge regression non exact t-type tests of the individual coefficients for the Probit regression model. A simulation study was conducted to evaluate and compare the performance of the test statistics with respect to their empirical size and power under different simulation conditions. Our simulations identified which of the proposed tests maintain type I error rates close to the 5% nominal level while simultaneously showing gains in statistical power over the standard Wald z-test commonly used in Probit regression models. Our paper is the first of its kind to compare tests for these different shrinkage approaches to estimation in Probit Ridge regression. The results will be valuable for applied statisticians and researchers in regression models.

Keywords: Empirical power; Probit regression; Ridge regression, Simulation study; Type I error rate, Multicollinearity.

1. Introduction

Multicollinearity arises when there are high inter-correlations among independent variables in a multiple regression model. This issue can make ordinary least squares (OLS) and Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) methods produce unstable and unreliable regression coefficients. Ridge regression, introduced by Hoerl and Kennard (1970), is a popular method to address this instability. By adding a bias term to the regression estimates, ridge regression significantly reduces variance and mean square error (MSE) compared to OLS. This technique has been extended to various generalized linear models, such as logistic, probit, Poisson, and beta regression, as demonstrated by researchers like Schaefer et al. (1984), Le Cessie (1992), Vago and Kemmeny (2006), Locking et al (2013) and others.

The ridge estimator depends on a crucial tuning/shrinkage parameter k , and numerous studies have focused on its estimation, including work by Hoerl and Kennard (1970), Kibria (2003), Khalaf and Shukur (2005), Muniz et al. (2012), Mansson et al. (2010), and Saleh et al. (2019).

Hypothesis testing is vital for evaluating the significance of regression model coefficients, facilitating variable selection. Halawa and El-Bassiouni (2000) introduced non-exact t-tests for ridge regression coefficients, showing that these tests have correct sizes and improved power over least squares t-tests for models with large standard errors, specifically for certain estimators of the shrinkage parameter k . Subsequent research, such as by Gokpinar and Ebeğil (2016), Kibria and Banik (2019), and Kibria and Perez-Melo (2020), confirmed the reliability of these tests. Kibria and Perez-Melo (2020) specifically examined forty different ridge regression t-type tests, validating their effectiveness in maintaining correct Type I error rates and enhancing power over OLS-based tests.

Testing coefficients for shrinkage in generalized linear models is still largely unexplored, except for a study by Cule et al. (2011), which extended Halawa and El-Bassiouni's non-exact t-type tests to ridge logistic regression. They achieved satisfactory results in Type I error and power over regular Wald tests based on unpenalized MLE estimators. However, their study did not compare performance across different shrinkage parameter estimation rules, nor has subsequent research addressed this for other generalized linear models.

To address this gap, our paper extends the non-exact t-type tests to probit regression models under ridge estimation, providing valuable insights for statisticians and researchers dealing with multicollinearity in regression models. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the proposed test statistics for the probit regression model. Section 3 presents a Monte Carlo simulation study comparing the performance of the test statistics. Section 4 analyzes a real-life dataset, and Section 5 offers concluding remarks.

2. Test Statistics for Probit Regression Coefficients

The term *generalized linear model* (GLM) refers to a larger class of models popularized by McCullagh and Nelder (1982, 2nd edition 1989). In these models, the response variable Y_i is assumed to follow an exponential family distribution with mean μ_i , which is assumed to be some (often nonlinear) function of $x_i^T \beta$, where β is $(q \times 1)$ dimensional unknown coefficient vector.

There are three components to any GLM:

- Random Component – refers to the probability distribution of the response variable (Y); e.g. normal distribution for Y in the linear regression, or Bernoulli distribution for Y in probit regression
- Systematic Component - specifies the explanatory variables $X_1, X_2 \dots X_q$ in the model, more specifically their linear combination in creating the so called *linear predictor*; e.g., $X^T \beta$
- *Link Function* $g(\mu)$ - specifies the link between random and systematic components. It says how the expected value of the response relates to the linear predictor of explanatory variables; e.g., $\eta = g(\mu) = X^T \beta$

In the case of probit regression $Y_i \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\pi_i)$

$$\eta = g(\mu) = \Phi^{-1}(\pi) = X^T \beta, \quad (2.1)$$

where $\Phi^{-1}(\cdot)$ is the inverse CDF, or quantile function, of a standard normal distribution, ie: $N(0,1)$

Hence,

$$\pi_i = \Phi(x_i' \beta) \quad (2.2)$$

where x_i is the i -th row of X matrix which is an $n \times (q+1)$ data matrix with q explanatory (or independent) variables and β is a $(q+1)$ vector of coefficients.

The coefficients of the model are estimated from the data through maximum likelihood estimation via numerical methods (iteratively weighted least squares), resulting in,

$$\hat{\beta}_{ML} = (X^T \hat{W} X)^{-1} X^T \hat{W} \hat{z}, \quad (2.3)$$

where $\hat{W} = \text{diag}\left(\frac{(\Phi(x_i' \beta))^2}{\Phi(x_i' \beta)(1-\Phi(x_i' \beta))}\right)$ and \hat{z} is a vector where the i -th element equals,

$$\hat{z}_i = \log(\hat{\pi}_i) + \frac{y_i - \hat{\pi}_i}{\hat{\pi}_i(1-\hat{\pi}_i)}.$$

To test whether the i -th component of the parameter vector β is equal to zero, the Wald test is used based on the MLE estimator:

$$H_0: \beta_i = 0 \text{ versus } H_1: \beta_i \neq 0$$

$$t = \frac{\hat{\beta}_i}{s(\hat{\beta}_i)} \quad (2.4)$$

where $\hat{\beta}_i$ is the i -th component of $\hat{\beta}_{ML}$ and $S(\hat{\beta}_i)$ is the square root of the i th diagonal element of $\text{Var}(\hat{\beta}_{ML})$, the estimated variance-covariance matrix of the last step of the iteratively weighted least squares algorithm. For large sample sizes and under the null hypothesis, this test statistic is distributed as $N(0,1)$ (see McCullagh and Nelder (1989)). However, when $X^T X$ is ill conditioned due to multicollinearity, the maximum likelihood estimator in (2.2) produces unstable estimators with unduly large sampling variance.

2.1 Probit Ridge Regression

In the case of linear regression, adding a constant k to the diagonal elements of $X^T X$ improves the ill conditioned situation, which is known ridge regression method. Ridge estimation has been

adapted to probit regression by Locking et al (2012) and the ridge regression of the parameter vector β is obtained as,

$$\hat{\beta}_{(k)} = (X^T \widehat{W} X + kI_n)^{-1} X^T \widehat{W} X \widehat{\beta}_{ML} \quad (2.5)$$

where $k > 0$ is the ridge, biasing or shrinkage parameter.

The variance-covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{(k)}$ is obtained as follows:

$$Var(\widehat{\beta}_{(k)}) = F_k Var(\widehat{\beta}_{ML}) F_k^T \quad (2.6)$$

where $F_k = (X^T \widehat{W} X + kI_n)^{-1} X^T \widehat{W} X$

To test whether the i -th component of the parameter vector β is equal to zero, Halawa and Bassouni (2000) proposed the following t-test statistic based on the ridge estimator of the parameter vector:

$$t_k = \frac{\widehat{\beta}_{i(k)}}{S(\widehat{\beta}_{i(k)})} \quad (2.7)$$

where $\widehat{\beta}_{i(k)}$ is the i th element of $\widehat{\beta}_{(k)}$ and $S(\widehat{\beta}_{i(k)})$ is the square root of the i th diagonal element of $Var(\widehat{\beta}_{(k)})$.

Under the null hypothesis, the test statistic (2.7) is assumed to be asymptotically $N(0,1)$ for a fixed value of k . Nevertheless when the value of k is estimated from the data, as in our paper, the argument may not be valid. Therefore, a suitable choice of k is important to make the tests keep an appropriate type I error. For more details on this topic, we refer our readers to Halawa and Bassiouni (2000) and Cule et al (2011).

Since the shrinkage parameter k is unknown, it must be estimated from the observed data. Numerous methods for estimating k exist in the literature. In this section, we present sixteen different ridge shrinkage parameter estimators from Locking et al. (2013), which will be analyzed in our simulation study for the test statistic defined in equation (2.7). Table 2.1 below lists these estimators. For detailed derivations, readers are referred to the original papers cited in the references.

Table 2.1. Ridge shrinkage parameter estimators.

Authors	Ridge estimator formula (k)
Hoerl and Kennard (1970)	$k_1 = \widehat{\sigma}^2 / \max(\widehat{\alpha}_j^2)$
Schaffer et al (1984)	$k_2 = 1 / \max(\widehat{\alpha}_j^2)$
Kibria (2003)	$k_3 = \text{Geometric Mean}(\widehat{\sigma}^2 / \widehat{\alpha}_j^2)$
Kibria (2003)	$k_4 = \text{Median}(\widehat{\sigma}^2 / \widehat{\alpha}_j^2)$

Muniz and Kibria (2009)	$k_5 = \max \left(1/(\widehat{\sigma}^2/\widehat{\alpha}_j^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)$
Muniz and Kibria (2009)	$k_6 = \max \left((\widehat{\sigma}^2/\widehat{\alpha}_j^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)$
Muniz and Kibria (2009)	$k_7 = \text{Geometric Mean}(1/(\widehat{\sigma}^2/\widehat{\alpha}_j^2)^{\frac{1}{2}})$
Muniz and Kibria (2009)	$k_8 = \text{Geometric Mean}((\widehat{\sigma}^2/\widehat{\alpha}_j^2)^{\frac{1}{2}})$
Muniz and Kibria (2009)	$k_9 = \text{Median}(1/(\widehat{\sigma}^2/\widehat{\alpha}_j^2)^{\frac{1}{2}})$
Muniz and Kibria (2009)	$k_9 = \text{Median}((\widehat{\sigma}^2/\widehat{\alpha}_j^2)^{\frac{1}{2}})$
Muniz et all (2012)	$k_{11} = \max(1/g_j) , \quad \text{where } g_j$ $= (\lambda_{\max}\widehat{\sigma}^2)/((n-q)\widehat{\sigma}^2 + \lambda_{\max}\widehat{\alpha}_j^2)$
Muniz et all (2012)	$k_{12} = \max(g_j)$
Muniz et all (2012)	$k_{13} = \text{Geometric Mean}(1/g_j)$
Muniz et all (2012)	$k_{14} = \text{Geometric Mean}(g_j)$
Muniz et all (2012)	$k_{15} = \text{median}(1/g_j)$
Muniz et all (2012)	$k_{16} = \max(g_j)$

Here, $\widehat{\alpha}$ is defined as:

$$\widehat{\alpha} = P^T \widehat{\beta} \quad (2.8)$$

where P is an orthonormal matrix that satisfies $P^T X^T \widehat{W} X P = \Lambda$, and Λ is a diagonal matrix of eigenvalues $(\lambda_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, q)$ of $X^T \widehat{W} X$, and $\widehat{\sigma}^2$ is the residual variance of the raw residuals divided by $n-q-1$ degrees of freedom. For details see Mansson (2011)

3. Simulation Study

To calculate the value of test statistics, we considered each of the shrinkage rules in the previous tables along with the Wald test and thus obtained 17 different values of the test statistics. Since a theoretical assessment among the test statistics was not possible, a simulation study will be conducted to evaluate the performances of the suggested tests in the following section.

Our simulation study has two parts. First, we analyzed the empirical Type I error of the tests. The test statistics that achieved the nominal size of close to 5% will be kept, and the ones that deviated significantly from the 5% size will be discarded. The second part of the simulation

study compared the tests statistics that achieved 5% nominal size, in regard to statistical power gains over the Wald test.

3.1. Type I Error Rates Simulation Procedure

R version 4.1.2 was used for all calculations and simulations. For the empirical Type I error simulation and the power of the test, we considered sample sizes $n = 50, 100, 300$ and 500 the number of regressors $q = 4, 6$ and 10 . To see the effects of multicollinearity by stating the correlation matrix among the regressors, we assumed $\rho = 0.6, 0.8$ and 0.95 . An $n \times q$ matrix X was created as $H \Lambda^{0.5} G^T$, where H is any $(n \times q)$ matrix whose columns are orthogonal, Λ is the diagonal matrix of eigenvalues of the correlation matrix, and G is the matrix of normalized eigenvectors of the correlation matrix, respectively.

Halawa and Bassiouni (2020), based their simulations on both the most favorable (MF) and least favorable (LF) direction of β for model (1). The MF orientation of β corresponds to the normalized eigenvector of the largest eigenvalue of the matrix $X^T X$, which is a vector of the form $(1/\sqrt{q})1_q$. The LF orientation is a unit vector orthogonal to $(1/\sqrt{q})1_q$. For a detailed explanation of MF and LF directions of β and other details of the simulation procedure, please see the paper by Halawa and Bassiouni (2020). They determined theoretically and empirically, and this has been confirmed by the other papers investigating these tests, that the LF orientation produces tests which keep the Type I nominal level no matter what estimator is used. On the other hand, some tests present a higher Type I error than they are supposed to, under the MF orientation of β . Therefore, from a practical standpoint the MF orientation is the one that allows us to discard tests that are overly liberal in rejecting the null hypothesis, therefore our simulation will be based on the MF orientation of β .

To estimate the 5% nominal size ($\alpha = 0.05$) for testing $H_0: \beta_i = 0$ versus $H_1: \beta_i \neq 0$ under different conditions, 3000 pseudo random vectors of n observations are obtained from the *Bernoulli* (π_i) distribution, where

$$\pi_i = \Phi(x_i' \beta) \quad (2.9)$$

Where x_i is the i -th row of X which is the $n \times (q+1)$ data matrix with q explanatory (or independent) variables and β is a $(q+1)$ vector of coefficients , as above.

Without loss of any generality, we let zero intercept for the model. Under the null model, substituting the i -th element of the considered MF β by zero. The estimated sizes were computed as the percentage of times the absolute values of all selected test statistics were greater than the critical value of $Z_{0.025} = 1.96$.

3.2. Type I Error Rates Simulation Results

In Tables 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3, we recorded the empirical sizes of the tests for the MF orientation for correlation levels of 0.60, 0.80 and 0.95, respectively.

Table 3.1. Simulated Type I errors for $\rho = 0.60$ and $\alpha=0.05$, MF orientation.

Statistics	q=4				q=6				q=10				rho=0.60 Average
	n=50	n=100	n=300	n=500	n=50	n=100	n=300	n=500	n=50	n=100	n=300	n=500	
tK0	0.061	0.055	0.064	0.054	0.067	0.058	0.041	0.058	0.07	0.070	0.056	0.048	5.9%
tK1	0.079	0.073	0.078	0.075	0.059	0.07	0.066	0.08	0.044	0.064	0.058	0.056	6.7%
tK2	0.079	0.071	0.078	0.075	0.057	0.072	0.066	0.079	0.042	0.062	0.058	0.056	6.6%
tK3	0.07	0.058	0.07	0.083	0.055	0.075	0.076	0.103	0.044	0.075	0.074	0.083	7.2%
tK4	0.068	0.053	0.072	0.071	0.05	0.068	0.068	0.087	0.043	0.062	0.066	0.073	6.5%
tK5	0.078	0.071	0.081	0.096	0.066	0.086	0.086	0.121	0.065	0.099	0.122	0.136	9.2%
tK6	0.077	0.076	0.085	0.1	0.068	0.1	0.114	0.125	0.065	0.108	0.150	0.185	10.4%
tK7	0.061	0.057	0.068	0.083	0.049	0.057	0.06	0.075	0.041	0.054	0.063	0.068	6.1%
tK8	0.067	0.058	0.072	0.087	0.052	0.061	0.064	0.083	0.04	0.059	0.064	0.063	6.4%
tK9	0.067	0.06	0.067	0.079	0.054	0.067	0.065	0.078	0.043	0.062	0.073	0.081	6.6%
tK10	0.063	0.063	0.068	0.079	0.055	0.059	0.067	0.08	0.039	0.056	0.057	0.057	6.2%
tK11	0.09	0.089	0.127	0.125	0.089	0.121	0.148	0.171	0.088	0.149	0.231	0.269	14.1%
tK12	0.054	0.054	0.065	0.058	0.052	0.057	0.04	0.057	0.038	0.053	0.055	0.047	5.3%
tK13	0.09	0.089	0.127	0.125	0.086	0.121	0.148	0.171	0.08	0.146	0.231	0.269	14.0%
tK14	0.054	0.054	0.064	0.058	0.056	0.057	0.04	0.057	0.031	0.053	0.056	0.047	5.2%
tK15	0.09	0.089	0.127	0.125	0.086	0.121	0.148	0.171	0.081	0.146	0.231	0.269	14.0%
tK16	0.055	0.054	0.064	0.058	0.056	0.057	0.04	0.057	0.04	0.053	0.056	0.047	5.3%

Table 3.2. Simulated Type I errors for $\rho = 0.80$ and $\alpha=0.05$, MF orientation.

Statistics	q=4				q=6				q=10				rho=0.80 Average
	n=50	n=100	n=300	n=500	n=50	n=100	n=300	n=500	n=50	n=100	n=300	n=500	
tK0	0.048	0.047	0.04	0.06	0.051	0.046	0.046	0.05	0.06	0.057	0.047	0.051	5.0%
tK1	0.071	0.093	0.077	0.096	0.063	0.078	0.076	0.075	0.03	0.051	0.052	0.063	6.9%
tK2	0.071	0.091	0.078	0.096	0.06	0.076	0.076	0.073	0.025	0.050	0.052	0.062	6.8%
tK3	0.069	0.091	0.091	0.107	0.065	0.092	0.103	0.084	0.056	0.083	0.083	0.112	8.6%
tK4	0.067	0.086	0.091	0.115	0.054	0.077	0.086	0.09	0.03	0.071	0.066	0.089	7.7%
tK5	0.109	0.12	0.136	0.148	0.121	0.167	0.183	0.194	0.125	0.257	0.249	0.338	17.9%
tK6	0.104	0.132	0.137	0.145	0.105	0.158	0.17	0.183	0.134	0.239	0.240	0.316	17.2%
tK7	0.084	0.099	0.1	0.114	0.079	0.113	0.12	0.122	0.051	0.118	0.112	0.164	10.6%
tK8	0.079	0.094	0.095	0.099	0.063	0.09	0.089	0.098	0.025	0.065	0.072	0.096	8.0%
tK9	0.091	0.104	0.11	0.122	0.086	0.124	0.133	0.137	0.069	0.138	0.138	0.192	12.0%
tK10	0.077	0.093	0.087	0.105	0.057	0.084	0.085	0.085	0.025	0.059	0.067	0.084	7.6%
tK11	0.119	0.147	0.181	0.171	0.145	0.207	0.259	0.262	0.155	0.326	0.384	0.474	23.6%
tK12	0.039	0.047	0.057	0.056	0.042	0.048	0.047	0.05	0.034	0.035	0.048	0.05	4.6%
tK13	0.118	0.147	0.181	0.171	0.141	0.203	0.259	0.262	0.134	0.311	0.384	0.473	23.2%
tK14	0.044	0.047	0.057	0.056	0.04	0.048	0.047	0.05	0.011	0.042	0.048	0.05	4.5%
tK15	0.118	0.147	0.181	0.171	0.142	0.203	0.259	0.262	0.129	0.309	0.384	0.473	23.2%
tK16	0.046	0.047	0.057	0.056	0.045	0.048	0.047	0.05	0.025	0.044	0.048	0.05	4.7%

Table 3.3 Simulated Type I errors for $\rho = 0.95$ and $\alpha=0.05$, MF orientation.

Statistics	q=4				q=6				q=10				rho=0.95
	n=50	n=100	n=300	n=500	n=50	n=100	n=300	n=500	n=50	n=100	n=300	n=500	Average
tK0	0.064	0.052	0.058	0.051	0.054	0.053	0.048	0.05	0.078	0.073	0.054	0.052	5.7%
tK1	0.08	0.082	0.082	0.084	0.043	0.056	0.055	0.049	0.032	0.050	0.053	0.053	6.0%
tK2	0.08	0.079	0.082	0.082	0.037	0.052	0.054	0.049	0.033	0.049	0.052	0.053	5.9%
tK3	0.079	0.095	0.083	0.096	0.066	0.065	0.082	0.082	0.053	0.058	0.071	0.074	7.5%
tK4	0.076	0.09	0.096	0.105	0.069	0.064	0.085	0.075	0.045	0.054	0.063	0.07	7.4%
tK5	0.146	0.17	0.198	0.178	0.231	0.292	0.301	0.326	0.287	0.457	0.523	0.551	30.5%
tK6	0.128	0.143	0.165	0.154	0.174	0.203	0.215	0.243	0.193	0.305	0.371	0.375	22.2%
tK7	0.133	0.146	0.171	0.161	0.201	0.253	0.256	0.278	0.235	0.351	0.403	0.422	25.1%
tK8	0.094	0.115	0.115	0.124	0.076	0.091	0.108	0.093	0.058	0.074	0.084	0.091	9.4%
tK9	0.139	0.15	0.18	0.168	0.205	0.267	0.271	0.296	0.244	0.374	0.440	0.457	26.6%
tK10	0.089	0.111	0.116	0.117	0.064	0.079	0.094	0.08	0.055	0.068	0.072	0.08	8.5%
tK11	0.153	0.173	0.205	0.185	0.237	0.303	0.313	0.338	0.291	0.481	0.550	0.575	31.7%
tK12	0.056	0.045	0.056	0.052	0.076	0.044	0.046	0.047	0.161	0.106	0.050	0.049	6.6%
tK13	0.156	0.173	0.205	0.185	0.243	0.304	0.312	0.338	0.203	0.462	0.549	0.575	30.9%
tK14	0.038	0.047	0.057	0.052	0.029	0.037	0.045	0.047	0.039	0.034	0.049	0.05	4.4%
tK15	0.153	0.173	0.205	0.185	0.226	0.304	0.312	0.338	0.247	0.453	0.549	0.575	31.0%
tK16	0.051	0.049	0.057	0.052	0.033	0.041	0.045	0.047	0.032	0.043	0.049	0.05	4.6%

If the true Type I error rate is 5%, then, for a simulation based on 3000 runs, the observed Type I error will be in the following interval 99.999% of the times $0.05 \pm 6 \sqrt{\frac{0.05 \times 0.95}{3000}} \approx (3\%, 7\%)$. Based on the above we discarded the tests with an observed average Type I error exceeding 7% across the simulated scenarios.

From the above tables, we observed the following:

- i) The tests based on the estimators K3 to K11, K13 and K15 have Type I errors way above the 5% nominal size in the case of the MF orientation. This behavior is even more pronounced as correlation increases, and therefore cannot be recommended since those tests are too liberal at rejecting a true null

The rest of the tests (including the test based on the MLE) were, on average, close to the nominal size of 5% for different sample sizes, number of variables, and levels of correlation analyzed, not surpassing on average our cutoff limit of 7%. Therefore, the tests based on the MLE, K1, K2, K12, K14 and K16 ridge estimators are the ones that will be compared in terms of statistical power below.

3.3. Statistical Power Simulation Procedure

After discarding the tests which exceed the nominal size of 5% significantly, the remaining test statistics will be compared in terms of power. Following the paper by Gokpinar and Ebegil (2016), we will replace the i -th component of the β vector by $J w(0)\beta_i$, where J is a whole positive number, and $w^2(0) = (1 + (q - 2)\rho) / [(1 - \rho)(1 + (q - 1)\rho)]$. We analyzed the cases of $J=1,3$

Table 3.7. Average gain in power over the Wald test for $\alpha = 0.05$, for correlation levels of 0.60, 0.80 and 0.95.

	Average Gain over Wald test								
	rho=0.60			rho=0.80			rho=0.95		
	J=1	J=3	J=5	J=1	J=3	J=5	J=1	J=3	J=5
tK1	5.1%	17.5%	24.5%	8.2%	25.5%	32.5%	9.2%	30.9%	36.2%
tK2	4.9%	17.0%	24.0%	7.8%	24.8%	31.9%	8.9%	30.5%	35.9%
tK12	0.0%	0.4%	0.9%	0.1%	1.4%	3.1%	2.8%	11.3%	22.0%
tK14	0.0%	0.3%	0.8%	0.0%	1.1%	2.4%	0.5%	5.3%	14.5%
tK16	0.0%	0.3%	0.8%	0.0%	1.1%	2.4%	0.6%	5.1%	13.7%

For a better visualization, we provide the observed maximum average gain in power (J=5) over the Wald's z test for $\alpha = 0.05$ in the following graph.

Figure 3.1 Average maximum gain in power over the Wald's z test for $\alpha = 0.05$ for correlation levels of 0.60, 0.80 and 0.95.

Based on the above results, we observed the following:

- i) All the Ridge non-exact t-type tests considered were as or more powerful than the Wald test on average for the simulated scenarios
- ii) Power gains increased as the true alternative hypothesis was further from zero null in all cases.
- iii) Power gains increased as correlation between the covariates increased
- iv) Among the considered non-exact t-type tests, the most powerful ones compared to the Wald test were tK1 and tK2 in all simulated scenarios.

Therefore, in the case of Probit Regression, in presence of multicollinearity, we recommend tK1 and tK2 over the Wald test for testing the significance of the coefficients in the model.

4. Application Example

In our application, we consider the dataset “myopia”, featured in the textbook, Applied Logistic Regression, by Hosmer, Lemeshow and Sturdivant (2013). It is available in the R package “aplore3”. It consists of measurements for n=618 subjects. The outcome variable for our model is the presence myopia that takes value 1 if the patient is myopic or 0 if not.

The explanatory variables in the logistic regression model include:

- **age**: The age of subjects at their first visit, providing insights into how age correlates with the likelihood of myopia.
- **spheq (Spherical Equivalent Refraction)**: This metric measures the overall refractive error of the eye, indicating its impact on myopia odds.
- **acd (Anterior Chamber Depth)**: A measure of the depth of the anterior chamber of the eye, offering insights into its role in influencing myopia odds.
- **lt (Lens Thickness)**: Representing the thickness of the lens in the eye, lt's coefficient in the model provides understanding regarding its impact on myopia development.
- **vcd (Vitreous Chamber Depth)**: Reflecting the depth of the vitreous chamber of the eye, vcd is another relevant metric influencing myopia odds.
- **spothr (Hours of sports/outdoor activities per week)**: The number of hours per week a subject spends engaging in sports or outdoor activities, contributing to the exploration of outdoor activities' potential protective effect against myopia.
- **readhr (Hours of reading for pleasure per week)**: The hours spent reading for pleasure per week, included to examine its association with myopia.
- **comphr (Hours of playing video/computer games per week)**: Accounting for the time spent playing video or computer games, its coefficient in the model provides insights into the relationship between screen time and myopia.
- **studyhr (Hours of studying/reading for school assignments per week)**: Measures the time spent on academic activities outside of school, shedding light on the impact of academic workload on myopia.
- **thyr (Hours of watching television per week)**: This variable represents the number of hours per week a subject spends watching television, adding an important dimension to our analysis of lifestyle factors affecting myopia.
- **al (Axial Length)**: Representing the axial length of the eye, al is a crucial metric for understanding the anatomical factors associated with myopia.

There is evidence of multicollinearity in the data, as measured by four of the variance inflation factors (VIFs) being greater than 10 (Ozkale and Kaciranlar, 2007), which is in practice considered the threshold for multicollinearity (Table 4.1). Also the Condition number (CN)

which is defined as $CN = \sqrt{\frac{\text{largest eigenvalue}(X^T X)}{\text{smallest eigenvalue}(X^T X)}} = 147$ is greater than 30 indicating high dependency between the explanatory variables.

Table 4.1: VIFs of the regressors

Variable	VIF
age	1.3
spheq	1.1
acd	3481.8
lt	1569.1
vcd	28997.7
spothr	1.1
readhr	1.1
comphr	1.0
studyhr	1.3
tyhr	1.1
al	30375.6

Since the problem of multicollinearity exists in the data, Ridge probit regression estimation is preferable to unconstrained MLE estimation for this model. We contrasted the results of the unconstrained MLE method with the shrinkage parameter estimator that showed higher power in our simulations (K1), and the analyses are given in the following Table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Regression Analysis Myopia Data

	Unconstrained MLE (K=0)			Ridge (K1 =1.69*10 ⁻⁵)		
	coef	z	p-value	coef	z	p-value
intercept	6.6369	1.575	0.115	6.6371	1.575	0.115
age	-0.1287	-1.057	0.290	-0.1287	-1.057	0.290
spheq	-2.3068	-9.584	<0.001**	-2.3066	-9.585	<0.001**

acd	6.9828	0.341	0.733	6.8076	0.342	0.733
lt	5.7738	0.282	0.778	5.5987	0.281	0.799
vcd	6.2087	0.303	0.761	6.0335	0.303	0.762
spothr	-0.0297	-2.658	0.007**	-0.0297	-2.659	0.008**
readhr	0.0465	1.757	0.078	0.0465	1.757	0.079
comp hr	0.0132	0.526	0.573	0.0132	0.561	0.574
studyhr	-0.0814	-1.643	0.100	-0.0814	-1.642	0.100
tyhr	-0.0046	-0.316	0.752	-0.0046	-0.315	0.753
al	-6.5050	-0.318	0.750	-6.3299	-0.318	0.751

In the case of the unconstrained probit regression, *spheq* and *spothr* are significant predictors at 5% level, while *readhr* is marginally significant (at 10% level). In this particular example the amount of shrinkage provided by K_1 is small ($K_1=1.69*10^{-5}$), hence the results of the probit ridge regression model are exactly the same in terms of significant variables. The coefficients in the probit regression model are similar in value to the ones in the MLE unconstrained probit model although somewhat smaller in absolute value, due to the effect of the shrinkage, as expected.

5. Some concluding remarks

In this paper, we investigated seventeen different test statistics based on MLE and Ridge estimators from the existing literature to evaluate the statistical significance of the regression coefficients of the probit regression model in the presence of multicollinearity. We conducted a simulation study under various conditions to empirically compare these tests with different shrinkage parameters estimators. The performance of the test statistics was assessed based on empirical size and power. Our simulations revealed that the tK_1 and tK_2 tests consistently achieved higher power gains compared to the Wald tests based on the MLE estimator, while maintaining a nominal size close to 5%. We therefore recommend these tests to statistical practitioners for testing probit regression coefficients when multicollinearity is present.

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